

$\left[\Delta E = \frac{e^2}{2r} \left(1 - \frac{1}{D} \right) \right]$ suggesting that the bond is predominantly ionic. The absence of formation of 1 : 3 complexes in the case of Pr(III) and Nd(III) indicates that these complexes have a greater tendency to undergo hydrolysis probably due to their lower stability.

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Kinetics of Reaction of Bromomethyl Phenyl Sulphoxide with Benzoate Ions

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THE study of bimolecular nucleophilic substitution reactions has received considerable attention during the last two decades¹⁻⁵. The kinetics of the reaction of phenacyl bromide with substituted anilines⁶, benzoate ions⁷ and naphthoate ions⁸ have been reported. Bromomethyl phenyl sulphoxide has been reported to be reactive in nucleophilic substitution reactions⁹ but no systematic kinetic study of the reaction of this compound with benzoate ions has been reported. The results of a detailed kinetic study of the reaction of this bromosulphoxide with a number of benzoate ions in 90% acetone-water (v/v) are reported here.

Experimental

Bromomethyl phenyl sulphoxide was prepared according to literature procedure¹⁰ and purified by vacuum distillation.

Commercial samples of benzoic acids were purified by recrystallization. Solutions of benzoate ions were prepared by dissolving the calculated quantity of the acid in aqueous sodium hydroxide solution and making up to the required volume with AnalaR acetone (E. Merck grade).

Solutions of bromomethyl phenyl sulphoxide and benzoate ion of appropriate concentrations in 90% acetone-water (v/v) were thermostated and mixed together to start the reaction. At suitable regular intervals of time, 10 ml aliquots of the reaction mixture were withdrawn and run into a mixture of nitric and acetic acids. The liberated bromide ion was estimated by titration against standard silver nitrate solution using eosin indicator. When the initial concentrations of the two reactants were equal, the second order rate constants, k (lit. mol⁻¹ sec⁻¹) were calculated using the expression

$$k = \frac{1}{t} \cdot \frac{x}{a(a-x)}$$

where a is the initial [PhSOCH₂Br] and x is [Br⁻] formed in time t (sec). When the initial concentrations were unequal, the values of k were calculated using the expression

$$k = \frac{2.303}{t(a-b)} \log_{10} \frac{b(a-x)}{a(b-x)}$$

where a is the initial concentration of bromosulphoxide, b the initial concentration of benzoate ion and x the concentration of bromide ion formed in time t (sec).

The reaction was studied at three different temperatures and the E_a values were calculated from the slope of the Arrhenius plot of $\log k$ vs $1/T$. Using these E_a values, the values of ΔH^\ddagger , $\log A$ and ΔS^\ddagger were computed.

Results and Discussion

The reaction follows second order rate law, first order each in bromosulphoxide and benzoate ion. This is evident from the constancy of the values of the second order rate constant at different initial concentrations of each of the reactants (Table 1).

TABLE 1—DEPENDENCE OF RATE ON [PhSOCH₂Br] AND [PhCOO⁻] SOLVENT: 90% ACETONE-WATER (v/v); TEMP.: 40°

[PhSOCH ₂ Br] mol. lit ⁻¹	[PhCOO ⁻] mol. lit ⁻¹	10 ⁴ × k (lit. mol ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹)
0.02	0.02	4.00
0.02	0.04	4.09
0.02	0.05	3.81
0.025	0.02	3.72
0.03	0.02	3.80
0.04	0.02	3.84

The second order rate constants and activation parameters for the reaction of bromomethyl phenyl sulphoxide with 13 benzoate ions are recorded in Table 2. The isokinetic relationship $\Delta H^\ddagger = \Delta H_0^\ddagger + \beta \Delta S^\ddagger$ is obeyed in the case of the reactions with

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 TABLE 2—RATE CONSTANTS AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR THE REACTION BETWEEN BROMOMETHYL PHENYL SULPHOXIDE AND BENZOATE IONS IN 90% ACETONE-WATER (v/v) [PhSOCH₂Br]=0.03 M [X-C₆H₄-COO⁻]=0.03 M

Substituent	10 ³ × k lit. mol ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹			E _a (K cal _s .mol ⁻¹)	log A	ΔH [‡] (K cal _s .mol ⁻¹)	-ΔS (e.u.)
	35°	40°	43.5°				
H	2.50	3.74	5.44	17.16	9.56	16.54	16.80
<i>o</i> -NH ₂	8.92	14.48	18.06	15.78	9.17	15.16	18.75
<i>m</i> -NH ₂	9.32	5.06	—	16.08	8.93	14.94	21.44
<i>p</i> -NH ₂	8.19	12.53	16.39	15.76	9.10	15.14	18.96
<i>o</i> -NO ₂	0.52	0.86	1.20	19.49	10.54	18.83	12.45
<i>m</i> -NO ₂	0.63	1.00	1.40	17.94	9.54	17.32	17.02
<i>p</i> -NO ₂	0.25	0.38	0.55	18.31	9.31	17.69	17.61
<i>o</i> -OH	5.15	7.86	10.28	15.96	9.04	15.34	19.24
<i>p</i> -OH	4.45	6.98	9.86	17.73	10.24	17.11	13.81
<i>o</i> -Cl	1.53	2.43	3.26	17.64	9.70	17.02	16.21
<i>p</i> -Cl	1.61	2.56	3.51	17.94	9.93	17.32	15.14
<i>o</i> -Br	1.66	2.58	3.52	17.39	9.55	16.77	16.84
<i>p</i> -CH ₃	3.40	5.22	7.44	17.95	10.27	17.33	13.62

m- and *p*-substituted benzoate ions and a plot of ΔH[‡] vs ΔS[‡] yields a straight line with slope, β (isokinetic temperature) = 366.7°K.

The correlation between the electronic nature of the substituents in the benzoate ion and the E_a values is rather poor. This indicates that E_a values do not correctly reflect the variation of the rate of the reaction with a change in the nature and magnitude of the electronic effect of the substituent. The large negative entropy of activation is as expected for an S_N2 reaction in which there is increased steric crowding at the reaction centre in the transition state.

The kinetic data indicate that electron-releasing substituents increase the rate of the reaction while electron-withdrawing substituents slow it down. The overall order of reactivity observed is

This reactivity order is largely true to expectation based on the inductive and mesomeric effects of the substituents. In the case of the *o*-hydroxy and *o*-aminobenzoate ions there is hydrogen bonding between the substituent and the carboxylate ion and it is difficult to assess the influence of this factor on the nucleophilicity of these ions. The higher nucleophilicity of the *m*-aminobenzoate ion relative to the unsubstituted benzoate ion is rather surprising. This is probably due to the indirect operation of the +M effect through relay being considerably strong¹¹ (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Influence of (-) at 2 (and 6) relayed to 1.

The Hammett equation was found applicable to this reaction and a plot of log k for the reaction of the *m*- and *p*-substituted benzoate ions against the corresponding σ values is linear (Fig. 2). From the

Fig. 2. Hammett plot for the reaction of bromomethyl phenyl sulphoxide with benzoate ions at 40°.

1. *p*-NH₂, 2. *p*-OH, 3. *p*-OH₂, 4. *m*-NH₂, 5. H, 6. *p*-Cl, 7. *m*-NO₂, 8. *p*-NO₂

slope of the plot, a value of -0.79 could be obtained for the reaction constant ρ for the reaction. The negative sign of ρ for the reaction unmistakably signifies that the reaction is facilitated by electron release from the benzene ring towards the reaction centre. The value of ρ in the present case is slightly higher than the value of -0.70 reported by Mishra *et al.*⁷ for the reaction of phenacyl bromide with benzoate ions, indicating a somewhat higher susceptibility of the reaction to the polar effects of ring substituents in the benzoate ion in the present case.

The applicability of the Brönsted equation was examined by plotting log k (at 25°) vs the pK_a of the corresponding conjugate acids of the *m*- and *p*-substituted benzoate ions. The plot is linear with a slope (α) of +0.75 and r=0.96, indicating an excellent fit with the Brönsted equation. The higher

value of α , the Brönsted coefficient in the present case compared to the value of 0.50 reported by Mishra *et al*⁷ for the reaction of phenacyl bromide with benzoate ions indicates a greater degree of bond formation between the nucleophile and the reaction centre in the present case.

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Terpenoids and Related Compounds.

Part XXX¹. The Configuration of the Hydroxyl Group of Putrol

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SESHADRI *et al*² reported the isolation of two closely related triterpenoids belonging to the 25-norfriedooleanane series namely putrone and its corresponding alcohol putrol from the leaves of *Putranjiva roxburghii*. Based upon physical data these workers suggested the structure of putrone as 3-keto-25-norfriedoolean-9(11)-ene (I) and that of putrol as 3 α -hydroxy-25-norfriedoolean-9(11)-ene (II). But they did not correlate these compounds

with a compound of known structure and stereochemistry. It was recently shown³ in this laboratory by direct correlation with a known friedoolean derivative that the structure (I) suggested by Seshadri *et al* for putrone was indeed correct.

Seshadri *et al*² also reported that putrone (I) underwent easy reduction with sodium borohydride to form an alcohol which was found to be identical with putrol (II). On the other hand putrol when oxidised with chromic acid afforded putrone (I). But considering the known⁴⁻⁶ hydride reductions of various 3-keto friedooleanane derivatives in which the newly generated hydroxyl group at C-3 always assumes the β -axial configuration, we believed that the correct structure of putrol would be 3 β -hydroxy-25-norfriedoolean-9(11)-ene (III) and not 3 α -hydroxy-25-norfriedoolean-9(11)-ene (II) as suggested by Seshadri *et al*.

It is known^{7,8} that reduction of 3-ketofriedooleananes with sodium and amyl alcohol always gives the thermodynamically more stable 3 α (equatorial) alcohol. We therefore reduced putrone (I) with sodium and amyl alcohol to furnish the 3 α -hydroxy compound (II) which was found to be different (mixed m.p., co-tlc and ir) from natural putrol. Further the acetate (IV) of this 3 α alcohol was also found to be different from putryl acetate (V)² derived from natural putrol. Thus the correct structure of putrol was (III).

In support of the above contention, the nmr spectra of a number of 3 α (equatorial) and 3 β (axial) acetoxy friedooleananes have been studied. The signal of the axial proton at position C-3 carrying an α -acetoxy group invariably appeared as a multiplet(1H) centered around δ 4.60 to 4.62 ppm. But the signal of the equatorial proton at C-3 carrying a β -acetoxy group invariably appeared as a triplet(1H) in a comparatively downfield region centered around δ 4.87 to 4.90 ppm. The acetate (V) prepared from natural putrol showed a triplet(1H) around δ 4.90 ppm. This fact established beyond doubt that the proton at C-3 of (V) was α (equatorial). Obviously the hydroxyl group of putrol was β -axial. Our investigation also established that nmr spectra can be used to determine the absolute configuration of the hydroxyl group at C-3 of friedooleananes. The results are shown below in Table 1.